

Nitration. Part IV. Nitration by Means of a Mixture of Nitrosulphonic and Fuming Nitric Acids.

BY P. S. VARMA AND SHYAMKISHORE SHARMA.

In a previous communication (Varma and Kulkarni, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **47**, 143) it has been shown that a mixture of nitrosulphonic and fuming nitric acids can be used as a nitrating agent and a number of nitro-derivatives could thus be obtained. The yield of the nitro-compounds so obtained was found to be quantitative in several cases and the products were, as a rule, free from by-products. Attempts have been made in this paper to study further the action of this nitrating agent on some more complex organic compounds. Two difficulties have been found in the experiments carried on in this connection. In some cases the reaction is so vigorous that special care has to be taken for preventing the charring of reacting mixture. This has been done either by adding an inert solvent such as chloroform or carbon tetrachloride to the reacting substance or by a very careful addition of the nitrating agent. To prevent charring at the end of the operation due to the action of the reacting mixture with water, the reaction products had to be handled very carefully in some cases.

From *p*-nitrophenol, sulphanic acid, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-aminobenzoic acids, *p*-dibromobenzene, benzoin, hydroquinone, cinnamic acid, α -nitronaphthalene, *p*-chlorophenol and *p*-iodotoluene, definite products have been obtained, though not necessarily the nitro-derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The nitrosulphonic acid mixture is prepared by passing a stream of sulphur dioxide into cold fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.502) until a mixture containing about 50 per cent. of nitrosulphonic acid is obtained. Most of the experiments described have been carried on at the room temperature (25-30°). The substance to be experimented upon is placed in a flask and dissolved in an inert solvent if

necessary and the nitrating mixture added drop by drop and shaken vigorously after each addition. If the reaction is too vigorous, the flask is cooled under tap water. When the whole of the nitrating mixture has been added, the flask is shaken frequently for another 15 minutes and warmed for a few minutes on a water-bath. The product is then diluted with water and the solid, if separated, is removed by filtration, washed and crystallised from some suitable solvent and identified. The results obtained are summarised in the table given below.

TABLE I.

Substance.	Amount of nitrating mixture added.	Product.
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol (5 g.)	20 g.	2 : 4-Dinitrophenol (1.5 g.)
Sulphanilic acid (10 g.)	"	{ <i>p</i> -Nitrophenol (2 g.) 2 : 4-Dinitrophenol (2.5 g.) 2 : 4 : 6-Trinitrophenol (0.5 g.)
<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid (10 g.)	"	Salicylic acid (5 g.)
<i>m</i> -Aminobenzoic acid (5 g.)	5 g.	3-Hydroxy-4-nitrobenzoic acid (1.5 g.)
<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid (5 g.)	10 g.	4-Hydroxy-3-nitrobenzoic acid (2 g.)
<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene (3 g.)	5 g.	2-Nitro-1 : 4-dibromobenzene (1.5 g.)
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol (2 g.)	3 g.	4-Chloro-2-nitrophenol (2.1 g.)
Cinnamic acid (4 g.)	10 g.	<i>o</i> -Nitrocinnamic acid (1.1 g.); <i>p</i> -nitrocinnamic acid (1.5 g.)
<i>α</i> -Nitronaphthalene (8 g.)	25 g.	1 : 3-Dinitronaphthalene (2.1 g.) 1 : 5-Dinitronaphthalene (1.5 g.)
<i>p</i> -Iodotoluene (5 g.)	10 g.	<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene (2.1 g.)
Benzoin (5 g.)	5 g.	Benzil (3.0 g.)
Hydroquinone (5 g.)	5 g.	Quinhydrone (1 g.); benzoquinone (1.1 g.)

With *p*-nitrophenol, the reaction is so vigorous that the reacting mixture required to be cooled under water, but it is comparatively smooth and on pouring the reacting mixture into water, 2:4-dinitrophenol crystallises out.

With sulphanilic acid the reaction is still more vigorous and the whole mass is charred if great care is not taken in adding the nitrating mixture very carefully. The product, after the addition of the nitrating mixture, is diluted with water very carefully and heated on a water-bath for about half an hour. There is a considerable frothing at this stage and the vessel is to be removed from the

water-bath from time to time so as to prevent the charring of the product. The solid separated is then fractionally crystallised from acetic acid and the crystals identified. Some more solid is obtained from the residual solution.

With *o*-aminobenzoic acid the reaction is so vigorous that each drop of the nitrating mixture produces a slight explosion and charring. By adding a few c.c. of chloroform, however, the reaction is moderated so that the formation of a tarry product is to a considerable extent prevented. From the resulting mass salicylic acid is extracted by boiling water and crystallised.

With *m*-amino- and *p*-amino-benzoic acids also the reaction is very vigorous. The substances are therefore dissolved first in chloroform (10 c.c.) and the sulphuric acid from the end products removed by the addition of barium chloride before they are concentrated and crystals obtained.

The reaction is smooth with *p*-dibromobenzene and the product is obtained without the addition of any diluent. With *o*-iodotoluene also the reaction is smooth but the iodine atom is in this case replaced by the nitro-group.

With *p*-chlorophenol, cinnamic acid and α -nitronaphthalene, the reaction is not so vigorous but each of them is dissolved in chloroform or carbon tetrachloride so that the reacting mixture could be brought into intimate contact with each other.

Benzoin and hydroquinone are not nitrated but converted into oxidation products.

